

The Influence of Tourist Attraction and Digital Marketing on Return Visit Interest with Tourist Satisfaction as a Mediating Variable in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency

Lipinikus Servinus Don Charles¹, Heru Tri Sutiono², Dyah Sugandini³

^{1,2,3} Universitas Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Yogyakarta, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The objectives of this study include: (1) To determine the effect of tourist attraction on tourist satisfaction at Tinalah tourist attraction, Kulonprogo Regency. (2) To determine the effect of digital marketing on tourist satisfaction at Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. (3) To determine the effect of tourist satisfaction on interest in visiting again at Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. (4) To determine the effect of tourist attraction on return visit interest in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, which is mediated by tourist satisfaction. (5) To determine the effect of digital marketing on return visit interest in the Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, which is mediated by tourist satisfaction. The research design used in this research was quantitative research design. The population used in this study were tourists visiting Tinalah Tourism Village, Tinalah, Kulonprogo Regency with a large and unknown number. The sampling technique used in this study is non probability sampling by purposive sampling. The respondents who met the criteria were tourists who had visited Tinalah Tourism Village with a maximum limit of the last three months. The research sample amounted to 150 people. The data collection procedure in this study is to use the questionnaire method. The analytical tool used is Partial Least Square (PLS), which is a variance-based SEM, with SmartPLS 2.0 software. Based on the results of the analysis discussed in the previous chapter, the following conclusions can be given: (1) Attractiveness of tourist objects has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. (2) Digital marketing has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. (3) Tourist satisfaction has a positive effect on interest in visiting again at Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. (4) Tourism attraction has a positive effect on interest in visiting again at Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, which is mediated by tourist satisfaction. (5) Digital marketing has a positive effect on interest in visiting again at Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, which is mediated by tourist satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Digital Marketing, Tourist Attraction, Tourist Satisfaction, Visit Interest

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the tourist destinations in Indonesia that is tourists' favorite is DIY. One of its main tourist attractions in Kulonprogo Regency is Tinalah Tourism Village. The number of tourist visits to Tinalah Tourism Village in 2023 reached 8,887 people, the majority of whom were local tourists reaching 8,740 people, while foreign tourists reached 147 people. The peak of tourist visits occurred in March, with the number of tourists reaching 1,074 people, while the quietest month for tourists was April with tourist visits reaching only 214 people.

Tinalah Tourism Village as one of the tourist attractions in DIY also strives for tourists to be willing to visit again. The interest in revisiting an object is a behavior that appears when customers are interested in the object and want to return quickly [1]. Customers who are interested in making return visits indicate that the company has given a good impression and is also able to meet customer expectations [2]. This is an important thing to do because with customers coming back to the company more often, the more frequent the use of the company's products [3]. The presence of unique elements or interesting differences in a tourist attraction can be an important factor that influences visitors' interest in returning to the place within a certain period of time. In other words, if a tourist destination has unique characteristics or elements that attract visitors, it is likely that visitors will be interested in returning to the place within a specified period of time. It shows the importance of the uniqueness or special appeal aspect in building a positive experience for visitors and stimulating their interest in making repeat visits [2]. Research by Ngajow, Tawas and Djemly

[4] proves that appeal has a positive and significant effect on interest in visiting tourist attractions. Research by Sappewali [5] also proves that tourist appeal has a positive and significant effect on interest in returning.

Another factor that tourism managers need to consider in optimizing the tourists' interest in returning is digital marketing. Currently, the interest of modern tourists that influences the decision to go on vacation or travel is largely influenced by recommendations from friends and relatives, online recommendations and comments by third parties [6]. Therefore, digital marketing can be managed well to provide online vacation recommendations to tourists. The information revolution and digitalization around the world have indeed changed the way media is consumed by the public. Technological advances and the development of communication technology have pushed real-world relationships to move to the virtual world. Consumer preferences are also shifting from traditional media forms to digital world consumption. People spend more time every day on digital media than traditional media. Over the past year, the number of social media users has even increased from 13%, and now there are 4.48 billion social media users worldwide, accounting for almost 57 percent of the world's total population (Habib et al., 2022).

The rapid development of digital technology which has caused the competitive strategy of digital tourism marketing is also needed to be adjusted. The ease of tourists in obtaining tourism information is the most important factor in determining the number of tourists coming to a country [8]. Social media is more influential than conventional marketing. It has a big impact on brands when social media is used wisely to promote the services and products [8]. The impact of technological developments on tourism is that tourists can understand the travel planning firstly by visiting the information site of the tourist destination they want to visit (Srisetia et al., 2023). Therefore, digital marketing needs to be managed optimally so that it can play a role in increasing the interest of tourists to return. The results of Hanifah's research [10] show that efforts to encourage the pace of the tourism sector include digital marketing and still paying attention to the store atmosphere aspect so that it can encourage tourists' interest in visiting. The findings of Azizah and Fathor AS's research [11] reveals that digital marketing has a significant influence on the interest in returning. The results of Armutcu et al.'s research [12] show that digital marketing interactions are one of the important determining factors of interest indeed in visiting tourist destinations.

Aprilia et al. [13] states that travel behavior carried out by tourists is the result of various factors. It is not enough to understand the behavior of tourists to revisit a tourist destination only due to motivational factors, attitudes and considerations of goals. Several previous studies tend to measure the intention of tourists to revisit through personal intuition and the desire to make recommendations [14]. The concept of revisit intention can also be shown through the desire to recommend, which means that tourists express a desire to revisit a destination and make recommendations to other friends because they are satisfied with their travel experience and this satisfaction experience will be part of word of mouth marketing [15]. Research by Sappewali, Saleh, and Suriani [5] proves that satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the intention to revisit. Research by Riadi, Permadi, and Retnowati [16] also proves that tourist satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the intention to revisit.

Satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment that someone feels after comparing what he expects with what he feels [5]. One factor that needs to be considered in optimizing tourist satisfaction is the attractiveness of the tourist attraction. Attractiveness affects tourist satisfaction, as stated by Suwanto [17] who stated that generally the attractiveness of a tourist attraction is based on the existence of resources that can create a sense of pleasure, beauty, comfort and cleanliness, and high accessibility to visit it. Research by Nestabiq and Seosanto (2021) proves that tourist attractions have a significant effect on satisfaction variables.

According to Primadi et al., [16] the determining factors for tourist satisfaction include physical evidence, emotional factors, attractiveness, accessibility, facilities, institutions and service quality. Digital marketing can be utilized by tourist attraction managers to introduce facilities and access to the location while optimizing tourist appeal. According to Sanjaya and Tarigan (2009) as quoted by Yanti [18], digital marketing is a marketing activity including branding that uses various web-based media such as blogs, websites, e-mail, adwords, or social networks. Of course, digital marketing is not just about internet marketing. The research findings of Azizah and Fathor AS [11] reveals that digital marketing has a significant influence on the intention to revisit and tourist satisfaction.

One of the tourist attractions in Kulon Progo that is currently being intensively promoted is Tinalah Tourism Village. The promotion is carried out through social media. However, in general, the social media of Tinalah Tourism Village is less attractive because it only displays the location and activities at the tourist attraction. In addition, some facilities are still inadequate, such as

the availability of clean water which is inadequate when there are many visitors, the condition of the toilets is not clean and there are no restaurants, so visitors have to leave the tourist area if they want to find food and drinks.

Based on the description above, it is interesting to study deeper about the "Influence of Tourist Attractions and Digital Marketing on the Intention to Revisit Mediated by Tourist Satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency".

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Return Visit Interest

Return visit interest occurs when tourists are satisfied after evaluating the results of their visit. Return visit interest is a research of various factors that influence tourist satisfaction [19]. There are several indicators of return visit interest according to Viet, Dang & Nguyen [20] as follow :

- a. Interested in traveling to the tourist attraction in the next few years
- b. Predicted to visit the tourist attraction again in the next few years
- c. The tourist attraction can be the next vacation spot.

2.2 Tourist Attractions

Tourist attractions are tourist objects that attract tourists to return. The attraction of a tourist destination is the main motivation for visitors to make tourist visits [21]. Tourist attractions according to Viet, Dang & Nguyen [20] include indicators of :

- a. scenery beauty such as beaches, islands, sand dunes and others
- b. Environment
- c. Entertainment and events.

2.3 Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is the activity of promoting and finding markets through online digital media using various means such as social networks [18]. Indicators of digital marketing variables according to Gomes, Antonio, Laot, and Gomes [22] are :

- a. Entertainment
- b. Interaction
- c. Trendiness.

2.4 Customer Satisfaction/Tourist Satisfaction

Engel et.al, [23] explain that customer satisfaction is an effective response to a specific consumption experience or an evaluation of the perceived suitability or non-suitability between previous expectations and the actual performance of the product after use. Tourist satisfaction in this study is more specific to tourist satisfaction in digital marketing. When online content provides accurate information, visual representations, reviews, personalization options, local insights, and support, these collectively contribute to setting expectations, creating excitement, and increasing overall satisfaction with the destination. By providing high-quality online content, tourism service providers can positively influence tourist satisfaction and encourage repeat visits and positive word-of-mouth recommendations (Armutcu et al., [12]. Indicators of tourist satisfaction in digital marketing include :

Online tourism information provides a positive image.

- a. A destination can display a strong image to tourists with online tourism content.
- b. Trustworthy online tourism information.
- c. Online tourism information updates.
- d. Online tourism information can be browsed in a relaxed manner (Armutcu et al., [12].

The hypotheses proposed in this study can be described as follows:

1. The attractiveness of tourist objects has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.
2. Digital marketing has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.
3. Tourist satisfaction has a positive effect on the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.
4. The attractiveness of tourist objects has a positive effect on the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency which is mediated by tourist satisfaction.

5. Digital marketing has a positive influence on the interest in returning to Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, which is mediated by tourist satisfaction.

Figure 1. Framework

3. METHODS

The research design used in this study is a quantitative research design. The object of this study is Tinalah tourism, Kulonprogo Regency. The population used in this study are tourists visiting Tinalah Tourism Village, Tinalah, Kulonprogo Regency with a large number but an unknown number. The sampling technique used in this study is non-probability sampling by purposive sampling. The respondents who meet the criteria are tourists who had visited Tinalah Tourism Village with a maximum limit of three months. According to Sugiyono [24] Sugiyono [24] in multivariate analysis, the minimum number of sample members is 10 times the number of variables studied. This study has 15 indicators, so the sample size needed is $15 \times 10 = 150$ people. The data taken in this study is primary data. The data collection procedure in this study uses the questionnaire method, namely a way of asking questions that have been prepared in writing by distributing questionnaires online and accompanied by answers that will be given to respondents. The analysis tool used is Partial Least Square (PLS), which is a variance-based SEM, with SmartPLS 4.1 software.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent description

Based on the research data obtained from 150 respondents related to the gender of the respondents, the data presented in table below is obtained :

Table 1. Respondent Groups by Gender

No.	Gender	Frequency	Percent (%)
1	Male	54	36,00
2	Female	96	64,00
Total		150	100,00

Based on the table above, it is known that most of the respondents in this study are women, reaching 64.00%

Table 2. Respondent Groups by Occupation

No.	Occupation	Frequency	Percent (%)
1	Student / College Student	16	10,67
2	Civil servant officer	18	12,00
3	Private employee	96	64,00
4	Self-employed	5	3,33
5	Housewife	6	4,00
6	Others	9	6,00
Total		150	100,00

Based on the table above, from 150 it is known that most respondents work as employees or private employees, namely 96 people or 64.00%.

Quantitative Analysis

a. Outer Model Test

1). *Convergent validity*

Table 3. Convergent Validity (Outer Loading) Test Result

	X1 Attractiveness	X2 Digital Marketing	Y Intention to revisit	Z. Satisfaction	Result
X1.1	0.708				valid
X1.2	0.759				valid
X1.3	0.716				valid
X1.4	0.756				valid
X1.5	0.798				valid
X1.6	0.739				valid
X2.1		0.748			valid
X2.2		0.722			valid
X2.3		0.759			valid
X2.4		0.712			valid
X2.5		0.775			valid
X2.6		0.735			valid
X2.7		0.767			valid
X2.8		0.709			valid
X2.9		0.830			valid
Y.1			0.753		valid
Y.2			0.786		valid
Y.3			0.708		valid
Y.4			0.793		valid
Y.5			0.780		valid
Y.6			0.718		valid
Z.1				0.791	valid
Z.2				0.724	valid
Z.3				0.779	valid
Z.4				0.860	valid
Z.5				0.714	valid

The table above shows that all indicators of the research variables have a loading factor value > 0.7. These results indicate that at this testing stage all indicators of the research variables are valid and have met the convergent validity test because all indicators have a loading factor value above 0.7.

2). *Discriminant validity*

Table 4. *Discriminat Validity (Cross Loading) Test Result*

	X1. Attractiveness	X2. Digital Marketing	Y. Intention to revisit	Z. Satisfaction	Result
X1.1	0.708	0.643	0.643	0.590	valid
X1.2	0.759	0.584	0.610	0.643	valid
X1.3	0.716	0.622	0.637	0.612	valid
X1.4	0.756	0.607	0.603	0.603	valid
X1.5	0.798	0.642	0.635	0.685	valid
X1.6	0.739	0.644	0.595	0.648	valid
X2.1	0.613	0.748	0.693	0.647	valid
X2.2	0.614	0.722	0.644	0.633	valid
X2.3	0.627	0.759	0.655	0.631	valid
X2.4	0.605	0.712	0.592	0.616	valid
X2.5	0.670	0.775	0.686	0.691	valid
X2.6	0.580	0.735	0.594	0.595	valid
X2.7	0.645	0.767	0.654	0.651	valid
X2.8	0.624	0.709	0.586	0.634	valid
X2.9	0.669	0.830	0.680	0.682	valid
Y.1	0.667	0.663	0.753	0.681	valid
Y.2	0.697	0.689	0.786	0.659	valid
Y.3	0.598	0.612	0.708	0.614	valid
Y.4	0.609	0.664	0.793	0.649	valid
Y.5	0.640	0.603	0.780	0.629	valid
Y.6	0.559	0.658	0.718	0.622	valid
Z.1	0.672	0.597	0.610	0.791	valid
Z.2	0.653	0.682	0.667	0.724	valid
Z.3	0.632	0.683	0.683	0.779	valid
Z.4	0.689	0.684	0.685	0.860	valid
Z.5	0.628	0.662	0.639	0.714	valid

The table above shows that all indicators that have passed the cross loading test (discriminate validity) are valid, because they exceed 0.7 and are greater than the loading values of other variables.

3). *Average variance extracted (AVE)*

Table 5. *Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Test Result*

	<i>Average variance extracted (AVE)</i>
Attractiveness	0.557
Digital marketing	0.565
Intention to revisit	0.573
Satisfaction	0.602

The table above shows that all latent variables have an AVE value > 0.5 so all latent variables are said to be valid.

4). *Composite reliability*

If the composite reliability value ≥ 0.7 , it is stated as reliable and if the composite reliability value < 0.7 , it is stated as unreliable. In addition, if the cronbach's alpha value ≥ 0.7 , it is stated as reliable and if the cronbach's alpha value < 0.7 , it is stated as unreliable. The results of the average composite reliability test from 150 respondents are shown in the following table.

Table 6. Composite Reliability Test Result

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability
Attractiveness	0.841	0.841
Digital marketing	0.903	0.905
Intention to revisit	0.851	0.852
Satisfaction	0.833	0.834

The data above shows that all latent variables have a composite reliability value ≥ 0.7 so they have a Cronbach's alpha value ≥ 0.7 so that all latent variables are said to be reliable.

b. Inner Model Test

1). Inner Model Test Result (structural model)

Table 7. Inner Model Test Output Result (Model Structural)

Test	Test Result
Coefficient of determination (R^2)	
Tourist Satisfaction (R_1)	0,788
Intention to revisit (R_2)	0,799
Q^2 predictive relevance	86,3%
$Q^2 = 1 - ((1-R_1^2)(1-R_2^2))$ $= 1 - ((1-0,788^2)(1-0,799^2))$ $= 1 - ((1-0,621)(1-0,638))$ $= 1 - (0,379 \times 0,362)$ $= 0,863$	

2). Picture of PLS-Alogaritm Model

The following is a picture of the PLS-Algorithm model of revisit interest.

Figure 2. PLS-Algorithm Model of Return Visit Interest

3). Interpretation

a). Determination coefficient (R^2)

Based on Table 7 the R^2 value on tourist satisfaction of 0.788 indicates that the percentage of tourist satisfaction can be explained through the variables of tourist attraction and digital marketing of 78.8%. The R^2 value on the intention to revisit of 0.799 indicates that the percentage of intention to revisit can be explained through the variables of tourist attraction, digital marketing and tourist satisfaction of 79.9%.

b). Q^2 predictive relevance

Based on the calculation of Q^2 predictive relevance in Table 4.12 is 0.863. It shows that the diversity of research data that can be explained by the research model is 86.3% while the remaining 13.7% is explained by other factors outside this research model. Based on these results, this research model can be stated to have good goodness-of-fit.

c). Path Analysis (Path Coefficient Test)

The second test is to see the significance of the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables by looking at the parameter coefficient value and the significance value of t statistics. The path coefficient evaluation is used to show how strong the effect or influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables; if the p-value $< \alpha$, it is said to be significant. The path coefficient value in the algorithm bootstrapping report can be seen by selecting the path coefficient.

Figure 3. Path Coefficient Results

Based on Figure 3, it can be explained that the largest path coefficient value is shown by the influence of digital marketing on tourist satisfaction of 0.494. The influence of the attractiveness of tourist objects on tourist satisfaction is 0.433, followed by the influence of digital marketing on visiting interest of 0.382, then the influence of tourist satisfaction on visiting interest of 0.313 and finally the influence of the attractiveness of tourist attractions on visiting interest of 0.247.

The description of the results shows that all variables in this model have a path coefficient with a positive number. This phenomenon indicates that if the greater the value of the path coefficient on one independent variable on the dependent variable, the stronger the influence.

c. Hypothesis testing

Table 8. Direct Influence Bootstrapping Results

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Result
X1 Attractiveness -> Y Intention to revisit	0.247	0.256	0.121	2.038	0.042	Accepted
X1 Attractiveness -> Z. Satisfaction	0.433	0.425	0.088	4.918	0.000	Accepted

X2 Digital marketing -> Y Intention to revisit	0.382	0.378	0.090	4.232	0.000	Accepted
X2 Digital marketing -> Z. Satisfaction	0.494	0.495	0.087	5.707	0.000	Accepted
Z. Satisfaction -> Y Intention to revisit	0.313	0.309	0.092	3.385	0.001	Accepted

1). First Hypothesis Testing

H₁ = The attractiveness of tourist objects has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.

Table 8 shows that the attractiveness of tourist objects has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. This is proven by the original sample value of 0.433 (positive) and the t-statistic value of 4.918 > 1.98 (t table) and the p-value of 0.000 < 0.05. This result means that the higher the attractiveness of tourist objects, the greater the satisfaction of tourists in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, thus **hypothesis 1 is accepted**.

2). Second Hypothesis Testing

H₂ = Digital marketing has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.

Table 8 shows that digital marketing has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency proven by the original sample value of 0.494 (positive) and the t statistic value of 5.707 > 1.98 (t table) and the p-value of 0.000 < 0.05. This result means that the higher the digital marketing, the more it will be able to increase tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, thus **hypothesis 2 is accepted**.

3). Third Hypothesis Testing

H₃ = Tourist satisfaction has a positive effect on the interest in revisiting Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.

Table 8 shows that tourist satisfaction has a positive effect on the interest in revisiting Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency proven by the original sample value of 0.313 (positive) and the t statistic value of 3.385 > 1.98 (t table) and the p-value of 0.000 < 0.05. This result means that the higher the tourist satisfaction, the higher the interest in revisiting Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, thus **hypothesis 3 is accepted**.

4). Fourth Hypothesis Testing

H₄ = The attractiveness of tourist objects has a positive effect on the interest in revisiting Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, which is mediated by tourist satisfaction

The indirect effect test is carried out by comparing the results of the direct effect on the path coefficient and the indirect effect on the specific indirect effect as seen from the Bootstrapping results.

Table 9. Bootstrapping Results of Direct and Indirect Effects of Tourist Object Attractiveness on the Interest in Revisiting

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Result
Direct Effect						
X1 Attractiveness -> Y Intention to revisit	0.247	0.256	0.121	2.038	0.042	Accepted
Indirect Effect						
X1 Attractiveness -> Z. Satisfaction -> Y Intention to revisit	0.135	0.133	0.053	2.545	0.011	Accepted

Based on the table above, first, the direct relationship between the attractiveness of tourist attractions and the interest in revisiting is seen. The original sample value is 0.247 (positive) and the t-statistic value is 2.038 > 1.98 (t table) and the p-value is 0.042

<0.05, so the attractiveness of tourist attractions has a positive effect on the interest in revisiting in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.

The original sample value of the indirect relationship is 0.135 (positive) and the t-statistic value is 2.545 > 1.98 (t table) and the p-value is 0.011 < 0.05, so the tourist satisfaction mediates the influence of the attractiveness of tourist attractions on the interest in revisiting in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. Thus, it can be concluded that the attractiveness of tourist attractions has a positive effect on the interest in revisiting in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency which is mediated by tourist satisfaction in a complementary manner (partial mediation), thus **hypothesis 4 is accepted.**

5). Fifth hypothesis testing

H₅ = Digital marketing has a positive effect on the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, mediated by tourist satisfaction

The indirect effect test is carried out by comparing the results of the direct effect on the path coefficient and the indirect effect on the specific indirect effect as seen from the Bootstrapping results

Table 10. Bootstrapping Results of Direct and Indirect Effects of Digital Marketing on Intention to Revisit

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Result
Direct Effect						
X2 Digital marketing - > Y Intention to revisit	0.382	0.378	0.090	4.232	0.000	Accepted
Indirect Effect						
X2 Digital marketing - > Z. Satisfaction -> Y Intention to revisit	0.155	0.151	0.048	3.226	0.001	Accepted

Based on the table above, the first look is at the direct relationship between digital marketing and the interest in returning to visit. The original sample value is 0.382 (positive) and the t statistic value is 4.232 > 1.98 (t table) and the p-value is 0.000 < 0.05, so the digital marketing has a positive influence on the intention to revisit in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.

The original sample value of the indirect relationship is 0.155 (positive) and the t statistic value is 3.226 > 1.98 (t table) and the p-value is 0.011 < 0.05, so the tourist satisfaction mediates the influence of digital marketing on the intention to revisit in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. So, it can be concluded that digital marketing has a positive effect on the interest in revisiting Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency which is mediated by tourist satisfaction in a complementary manner (partial mediation), thus **hypothesis 5 is accepted.**

The attractiveness of tourist objects has an effect on tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency

Based on the results of the first hypothesis test that was carried out previously, the results shows that the attractiveness of tourist objects has an effect on tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. The effect is positive which can be seen from the original sample (0.433/positive) meaning that the higher the attractiveness of the tourist objects, the higher the satisfaction of tourists in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.

Setiawan, Saufi and Rinuastuti [25] argue that the success of a tourist attraction to reach a tourist area is very dependent on the attractiveness of the tourist attraction, such as the level of uniqueness, value of the tourist attraction, availability of land, and the physical condition of the tourist attraction that is easy to reach (accessibility), such as the distance from the highway and the condition of the tourist attraction, roads and vehicles to tourist attractions, facilities (amenities) such as public facilities (food stalls, toilets) and supporting facilities (places of worship, electricity, and parking lots). Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency has beautiful panoramas such as the attractive natural scenery and green areas that are pleasing to the eye. Tinalah Tourism Village also has a tourist-friendly environment, the diversity of nature around Tinalah Tourism Village adds to the attraction for tourists. The variety of entertainment and activities in Tinalah Tourism Village makes the holiday experience enjoyable and an attractive choice.

Digital marketing influences tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency

Based on the results of the second hypothesis test that was previously carried out, it is found that digital marketing influences the tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. The influence is positive which can be seen from the original sample (0.494/positive), meaning that the higher the digital marketing, the higher the tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.

Digital marketing and promotion by the tourism attraction managers will significantly impact on the overall tourist arrivals (Roy, 2020 in Bedi & Sharma, 2023). However, digital marketing and destination promotion itself may not be a panacea for creating more tourist demand, but at the same time, digital marketing can provide new insights into the uniqueness, potential, charm, and features that they naturally have (Kumar & Mishra, 2021 in Bedi & Sharma, 2023).

Tourist satisfaction influences the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency

Based on the results of the third hypothesis test that was conducted previously, it is found that tourist satisfaction influences the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. The influence is positive which can be seen from the original sample (0.313/positive) meaning that the higher the tourist satisfaction, the higher the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.

Consumers or customers who are satisfied will make repeat visits in the future and tell others about the services they feel (Fornell in Setiawan, Saufi and Rinuastuti [25]. The experience during the vacation has a high response from respondents. Tourists' interest in visiting is created from the satisfaction they feel. If tourists are satisfied with the tourism products and services provided, the tourists will want to return to the tourist spot and become loyal tourists.

The attraction of tourist objects influences the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, which is mediated by tourist satisfaction

Based on the results of the fourth hypothesis test that was previously conducted, the results show that the attraction of tourist objects influences the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, which is mediated by tourist satisfaction. The influence is positive, which can be seen from the original sample (0.135/positive), meaning that the higher the attraction of the tourist object, the higher the tourist satisfaction and will increase the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. It shows that tourist satisfaction plays a full role in mediating the influence of the attraction of tourist objects on the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village. This is supported by research conducted by Sappewali, Saleh, and Suriani [5] which proves that tourist satisfaction plays a full role in mediating the influence of the attraction of the destination on the intention to revisit.

Destination attractiveness has four main factors, namely accessibility, facilities and infrastructure, scenery, and local communities, all of which have the potential to encourage tourists to come and spend time at a destination (Henkel et al., 2006 in Pratminingsih et al., 2022). When visiting a tourism destination, tourists with high revisit intentions tend to be aware of the importance of the destination, are committed to making a positive contribution to the destination, and demonstrate actions aimed at protecting the destination for both current and future visitors [26]. Tourist satisfaction is the result of tourists' experiences during their visit to the destination. When a tourist attraction has high appeal, tourists tend to be satisfied with their experience [2]. This satisfaction does not only come from physical appeal, but also from other factors such as service, cleanliness, and comfort of the tourist attraction [8].

Digital marketing influences the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, mediated by tourist satisfaction

Based on the results of the fifth hypothesis test that was previously conducted, it is found that digital marketing influences the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency, mediated by tourist satisfaction. The influence is positive, which can be seen from the original sample (0.155/positive), meaning that the higher the digital marketing, the higher the tourist satisfaction and increases the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency. It shows that tourist satisfaction plays a full role in mediating the influence of digital marketing on the intention to revisit Tinalah Tourism Village. Research conducted by Azizah and Fathor AS [11] proves that tourist satisfaction plays a partial role in encouraging digital marketing on the intention to revisit. Digital marketing that is widely used to optimize the intention to revisit is social media. Research conducted by Agustini, Sudiarta and Suardana [27] proves that tourist satisfaction plays a partial role in encouraging social media in increasing the intention to revisit.

Digital marketing provides many-to-many communications facilities due to its high level of connectivity and in practice digital marketing can promote its tourist destinations effectively, relevantly, and cost-effectively [28]. The ability to communicate directly with potential tourists to get feedback through social media platforms is also an important factor in influencing tourist satisfaction and return intention (Verduyn et al, 2017 in Haudi et al., 2022). Overall, tourist satisfaction mediates the influence of digital marketing on return intention by strengthening the relationship between digitally delivered information and satisfying tourist experiences [12]. Digital marketing may be able to attract initial visits from tourists, but tourist satisfaction is the determining factor whether they will return or not [26].

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis that have been discussed in the previous chapter, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The attractiveness of tourist objects has a positive effect on the tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.
2. Digital marketing has a positive effect on the tourist satisfaction in Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.
3. Tourist satisfaction has a positive effect on the interest in revisiting Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency.
4. The attractiveness of tourist objects has a positive effect on the interest in revisiting Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency which is mediated by tourist satisfaction.
5. Digital marketing has a positive effect on the interest in revisiting Tinalah Tourism Village, Kulonprogo Regency which is mediated by tourist satisfaction.

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